

ENHANCING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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“Theoretical Aspects of the English Language”

Annotation. The world appeared on earth, and science surrounded us with its own light. The younger generation is also increasingly interested in learning new languages. This article discusses the development of intercultural communication competence in foreign language teaching and the further improvement of cultural relations between the two countries. This article is designed to help language learners not only learn the language itself, but also learn about the nation, religion, culture, national customs, life, and the way people communicate with each other. It also discusses the insufficient development of language competence in the environment where students are learning a foreign language, and several solutions have been proposed.

Keywords: etiquette, worldview, national animals, landscapes, historical monuments, taboos, innovation

Аннотация. Мир явился на земле, и наука озарила нас своим светом. Молодое поколение также проявляет все больший интерес к изучению новых языков. В данной статье рассматривается развитие межкультурной коммуникативной компетенции в обучении иностранным языкам и дальнейшее улучшение культурных связей между двумя странами. Эта статья призвана помочь изучающим язык не только овладеть самим языком, но и узнать о нации, религии, культуре, национальных обычаях, быте и способах общения людей друг с другом. В ней также обсуждается недостаточное развитие языковой компетенции в среде, где студенты изучают иностранный язык, и предлагается ряд решений.

Ключевые слова: этикет, мировоззрение, национальные животные, пейзажи, исторические памятники, табу, инновации.

Annotatsiya. Yer yuzida dunyo paydo bo'ldi va ilm-fan bizni o'zining nuri bilan o'rab oldi. Yosh avlod ham tobora ko'proq yangi tillarni o'rganishga qiziqmoqda. Ushbu maqola xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda madaniyatlararo muloqot kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish va ikki mamlakat o'rtasidagi madaniy aloqalarni yanada yaxshilash masalalarini muhokama qiladi. Maqola til o'rganuvchilarga nafaqat tilning o'zini o'rganishga, balki millat, din, madaniyat, milliy urf-odatlar, turmush tarzi va odamlarning bir-biri bilan qanday muloqot qilishlari haqida ham bilib olishlariga yordam berishga mo'ljallangan. Shuningdek, unda talabalar xorijiy tilni o'rganayotgan muhitda til kompetensiyasining yetarli darajada

rivojlanmaganligi va bir qator yechimlar taklif etilganligi ham muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: odob-axloq qoidalari, dunyoqarash, milliy hayvonlar, manzaralar, tarixiy obidalar, ta'qiqlar, innovatsiyalar.

Introduction:

In today's global world, developing intercultural communication competence is becoming increasingly important in teaching foreign languages. First of all, if we want to define the word culture in a country, we must take into account the language, values, beliefs, religion, lifestyle, worldview, and norms of behavior in society. Culture is different in every country and is passed down from generation to generation. For example, we show society how we are through our behavior, our upbringing, our language, our good and bad words, and our speech, our upbringing, our behavior, when we travel to other countries, during communication. Thus, culture is not individual, but is formed during communication in society or as a result of social processes. Therefore, every person learning a language should not only learn grammar, vocabulary, listening, and writing, but also learn how to use the language they are learning, learn about the culture of the language, and develop their skills during communication.

Methods

Intercultural communication competence refers to a person's ability to communicate effectively and quickly with people from other countries. The composition is divided into several parts.

1. Similarities between cultures between the two countries:

In this case, the person learning a new language must also learn the differences, similarities, cultural stereotypes, and cultural clashes between the two countries.

2. Knowledge of language and culture:

Every country has its own unique teaching style. For example, a person who is learning a language without knowing any of these subjects, such as history, etiquette, geography, politics, and economics, will unknowingly go to that country and experience culture shock. The above subjects are therefore necessary.

3. The most important thing for those who are learning a language is a warm attitude:

Everyone should be respectful and open to other cultures and not forget to smile.

4. Getting to know the culture of the country where the language is spoken

Results and Discussion

When teaching a language, the teacher should not limit himself to customs and traditions, but rather, the teacher should also provide the younger generation with information about the customs and traditions of that country, national animals and landscapes, festivals, weather, taboos, holidays, art, music, literature, famous films, songs, historical monuments, and other normative monuments. As students acquire new information, their self-confidence and worldview increase as they acquire new language.

Types of competence	Definition
Cultural knowledge	values, beliefs, customs, geography, history, and other cultures
Cultural skills	adaptability, stereotypes, ability to show empathy
Cultural attitude	respect, curiosity, openness, patience

To sum up, it examines the importance of intercultural communication competence in every individual in society and several ways to develop it in the process of teaching foreign languages. In the era of globalization, that is, the digital economy, learning not only involves learning languages, but also the ability to establish dialogue between different cultures. The research in the article suggests that various cultural role-playing games and interactive activities in the learning process help students expand their intercultural understanding and maintain a warm relationship with representatives of other cultures. This is an important step in preparing students to successfully operate on a global scale. Future research should focus on developing a new set of innovative approaches in this area.

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